

Geographic Information System Shortest Route Recommendation for Base Transceiver Station Location in Semarang Regency

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 14 May 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Agung Rahmad Hidayat</p>	<p>Base transceiver station (BTS) towers serve to connect mobile devices with operator networks by sending and receiving radio signals to and from communication devices. The strength of the received signal is influenced by the distance between the BTS tower location and the device, the farther the weaker. In addition, the quality of the signal is affected by disturbances on the BTS tower itself such as infrastructure damage, blackspots, and extreme weather conditions. There are 288 BTS towers scattered in Semarang Regency, owned by telecommunication tower providers and mobile operator networks. Each BTS tower requires regular maintenance to ensure the signal quality remains stable. With the large number of towers, a shortest route-finding system is needed to facilitate maintenance staff to get to the tower location. This study aims to examine the geographic information system (GIS) in recommending the closest path to the tower that needs to be repaired using Dijkstra and A* (A-star) algorithms. Dijkstra finds the shortest path by calculating the total weight of all points that need to be passed to reach the destination. A-star searches for a path based on the estimated value of the total weight of the points passed using Euclidean Distance. The route search process by determining the starting point, then selecting the location of the BTS tower, and looking for the shortest route based on possible major roads to the tower using Dijkstra and A-star algorithms. The two algorithms will be compared based on the speed in getting the closest route. GIS testing is carried out using the Black-Box Testing method with Boundary Value Testing techniques to ensure conformity between software and requirements specifications. System testing 82 routes to BTS towers using Dijkstra and A-star, with the average result that Dijkstra is 10 times faster in finding the shortest route than A-star. The result of this research is a geographic information system for finding the closest route to the BTS tower in Semarang Regency. The recommended route is based on major roads in Semarang Regency.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Base Transceiver Station, Shortest Route, Geographic Information System, A-star, Dijkstra</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

Telecommunication transmitter stations in the form of towers are known as Base Transceiver Stations (BTS), which function to transmit and receive radio signals to communication devices through antennas [1]. The radio signal is then converted into a digital signal through a transceiver, encrypted according to the operator's protocol into a data packet using technology standards such as Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM), Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA), Long Term Evolution (LTE), Time Division Multiple Access (TDMA), and General Packet for Radio Service [2]. In addition to towers and antennas, BTS is equipped with a shelter as a storage place for

telecommunication transmission support devices such as batteries, power supplies, air conditioners, and combiner.

Department of Communication and Informatics Semarang, Indonesia recorded a 45% growth in BTS towers in Semarang Regency over the period 2020-2023, with a total of 288 towers [3]. These towers are spread over an area of 950.20 km² and serve more than 800 thousand cellular phone users. Each BTS tower is used by multiple telecommunications network operators, such as Telkomsel, Indosat, and XL, through a shared tower scheme with separate transmitters and network antennas. However, ownership of the towers is not independently owned by all operators, most of which are owned by telecommunications infrastructure companies, such as Mitratel,

IBST and Protelindo, to avoid duplication of infrastructure, reduce operational costs and expand coverage.

Tower owners are required to perform routine tower maintenance and care to prevent communication interference. Tower disruptions have prevented many telecommunication operators from providing communication services [4], which has resulted in a decrease in customer satisfaction. The large number of BTS towers in Semarang regency makes it difficult for technicians to identify the location of a particular tower, potentially slowing down the response to technical problems.

Finding the location of BTS towers that need to be repaired, a technician needs a navigation tool, namely a travel route system in the form of a geographic map or Geographic Information System (GIS). GIS utilizes Global Positioning System (GPS) and remote sensing technology to solve problems related to spatial aspects by analyzing and visualizing geographic information [5], [6]. Deviati [7] used GIS to map the route of sediment deposition areas in the watershed of Aceh Province, Indonesia. In agriculture, GIS is used to map potential biomass energy crops [8]. In addition to mapping areas, GIS is used to recommend travel routes.

GIS recommends an optimal path based on shortest route-finding algorithms. Commonly used algorithms to determine the optimal route between two locations include Dijkstra [6], [9], [10], A* (A-star) [11], particle swarm optimization, and Bellman-Ford. Oh [6] implemented Dijkstra in an emergency vehicle navigation system (ambulance, and fire department) to respond to emergency events. Li [11] combined A* with a nature-inspired metaheuristic for gas leak location search, utilizing environmental change adaptation. Martins [12] developed a variant of the A* algorithm that is more efficient in finding routes on large-scale graphs with many vertices. Based on the reliability of Dijkstra and A* algorithms, it is possible to be implemented in route finding for BTS towers.

This research aims to develop a web-based geographic information system to assist technicians in determining the fastest route to the location of BTS towers in Semarang Regency that require repair. In determining the fastest route, the system utilizes the A* and Dijkstra algorithms as the basis for calculating the optimal path. The selection of the two algorithms is based on their ability to complete a single-source shortest route search. In this article, the steps of the implementation process of the geographic information system, A*, and Dijkstra are discussed in Chapter II of the research method including requirements analysis, geographic information system design, and algorithm and interface performance evaluation. Furthermore, Chapter III discusses the results of the design and evaluation of the route-finding geographic information system. It ends with conclusions related to the geographic information system for finding the shortest route to the BTS tower.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

In the research, the research process of building a geographic information system for finding the shortest route to a BTS tower goes through the following stages. The initial stage involves the

analysis of functional and non-functional system requirements, which serve as a reference point for the subsequent construction of the system. The subsequent stage entails the conceptualization of a geographic information system and route search, employing the Dijkstra and A* algorithms. The study concluded with a system evaluation employing the Black-Box method.

A. Dataset

This research uses secondary data on the location of Base Transceiver Station towers in Semarang Regency with a total of 288 locations [3]. This data was collected in 2023 by the Department of Communication and Informatics Semarang, Indonesia. In addition to determining the route, highway intersection data was collected, using the API from Open Street Map (OSM). OSM is an open-source map service developed through the Volunteered Geographical Information (VGI) concept to produce a worldwide geographic database. Road intersection data is taken based on the type of road based on public roads or roads that are often traveled by four-wheeled and two-wheeled vehicles. The overall geographical coordinates of the road intersection point, and tower locations used to determine the shortest route path are stored in a MySQL database.

B. Software Requirements Analysis

Requirements analysis is the process of describing the needs of both limitations and functionality in software development. The functional requirements of the software in this study are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE I: FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS SIG APPS

ID	Deskripsi
KF_01	The system can show tower BTS data
KF_02	User can select the tower they want to visit
KF_03	Users can get the shortest route to the BTS tower using Dijkstra's algorithm
KF_04	Users can get the shortest route to the BTS tower using A* (A-star) algorithm

C. System Design

Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a standard visual modeling language in software engineering for defining requirements, system analysis, architectural design, and implementation based on object-oriented programming paradigm [13], [14]. The system was developed for technicians to be the main users. Technicians are responsible for repairing and maintaining BTS towers. The goal of this system is to find the shortest route and the location of BTS towers. The user can input the current location and tower location destination. The system will search for the closest route based on user input using Dijkstra and A* algorithms. The system will display execution time, distance traveled, and route search results in the form of graphs and maps. The system design stages consist of use case, sequence, activity, and flowchart diagrams as follows:

1) **Use Case Diagram:** Use case diagrams illustrate how the system should work [13]. This diagram describes the functional requirements of a system and visualizes the interaction between actors and the system [15]. Figure. 1 shows the functional needs of the shortest route recommendation geographic information system in the use case diagram.

Figure 1 use case diagram user

2) **Activity Diagram:** Activity diagrams describe the workflow of the system through a series of sequences of processes in the system [14]. It is often used to extend the details in the use case diagram by modelling business processes or operational logic. This diagram helps understand the overall process in the system. Figure. 2 shows the activity diagram of the system.

Figure 2 Activity Diagram.

3) **Sequence Diagram:** Sequence Diagrams are used to describe the interaction between components in a system sequentially. Figure. 3 shows the Sequence diagram of the system.

Figure 3 Sequence diagram of geographic information system

4) **Flowchart Diagram:** The flowchart diagram in Fig. 4 explains the flow of the route-finding process using Dijkstra and A*.

Figure 4 flowchart diagram of shortest route search

D. Dijkstra

Dijkstra's algorithm is a shortest path finding algorithm from the origin node to the destination node by calculating the smallest weight of each path provided [16]. The weight or distance between two vertices is a positive number, otherwise it will result in an infinity solution [7]. This algorithm was discovered by Edsger W. Dijkstra in 1959, by utilizing graph theory and the adjacency matrix. A graph is described as a set of vertices (Vertex) connected by a set of lines (Edges), denoted as [17]. The adjacency between vertices is determined by the existence of a line connecting a pair of vertices. Each connecting line has a certain weight value to become a weighted graph. Dijkstra updates the shortest distance from the starting point to all other points in the non-negative weighted graph incrementally and eliminates routes with longer distances [18]. The function of calculating the shortest distance is notated as follows:

$$dist[v] = \min(dist[v], dist[u] + length(u, v)) \quad (1)$$

Where $dist[v]$ is the shortest distance to point v , while $length(u,v)$ is the distance weight of point u to point v . The steps of Dijkstra's algorithm in finding the shortest path are as follows:

1. Initialize the set of all points that have not been processed or passed. Set the starting point as the current point with a weight of 0 and set an infinite value for the weight from the starting point to all other points.
2. Calculate the weight of each point neighboring the current point. The point with the smallest weight is added to the route. The route from the starting point to the new point is the smallest weight of all routes to unvisited points.
3. The newest point is selected as the current point which will be used to calculate the weights from the newest current point to all unselected points.
4. The process of the second and third steps is repeated until all points have been processed or visited. The process will end when the shortest path from the starting point to every point in the graph has been found. The shortest path between the starting point and the destination point is selected as the solution.

E. A* (A-star)

The A* algorithm has similarities with Dijkstra, but A* combines actual costs with a heuristic estimation function of the shortest distance or weight of a point n to the destination to speed up the search [12]. The shortest route calculation in A* uses the following formula:

$$f(n) = g(n) + h(n) \tag{2}$$

Where, $g(n)$ is the actual distance from the starting point to the current point n while $h(n)$ is the heuristic function from the current point n to the destination point [19]. Euclidean Distance calculation is one of the estimation functions often used in the A* Algorithm, other than can use Manhattan Distance, or Diagonal Distance. The Euclidean distance calculated used equation 2.

$$h(n) = \sqrt{(x_n - x_{goal})^2 + (y_n - y_{goal})^2} \tag{3}$$

The steps of the A* algorithm in finding the closest route are as follows [20]:

1. Initialize the starting point.
2. Calculate all weights connected to the starting point.
3. If the candidate point is the destination, then stop and route is that point.
4. Otherwise, calculate the weight value of the connected point and the smallest weight makes the current point.
5. Repeat the third step until the shortest route is obtained.

F. Black-box Testing

Black-Box testing focuses on testing the functional specifications, input, and output of the application according to the software requirement, without considering the design and

program code. This evaluation is conducted from the perspective of the end user, with the aim of assessing the program's or software's behavior. Black-Box assists in identifying unmet aspects of the requirement specification based on the functions provided [21]. One of the Black-Box tests is Boundary Value Testing, which tests by dividing the input domain into data groups. In this study, we tested the login form, registration form, and route search function.

III. RESULT AND DISSCUSSION

A. Implementation Geographic Information System

The web-based geographic information system is implemented using the CodeIgniter framework with the PHP (Hypertext Processor) programming language. In this research, two distinct user types are identified: ordinary users and admin users. The distinction between the two lies in the administrative privilege to add new users.

In Figure 5, the login page serves the purpose of user verification. The login interface comprises a username field, password entry field, and a login button. If the user is not registered, they can register by selecting the “Sign Up” button.

Figure 5 Login user page

After clicking the “Sign Up” button, the user will be directed to the registration page, shown in Figure 6. The following fields must be completed in order to register a user in the system: full name, username, password, and password confirmation.

Figure. 6 User registration page

After the user successfully logs in, the system will be redirect to Dashboard page. There are five menus that can be selected, such as Dashboard, Data, Results, User and Logout pages. The logout menu is used to exit the system, which will then redirect the user to the login page.

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Figure. 7 Home dashboard

Dashboard page in Fig. 7, shown a geographical map BTS tower in the Semarang Regency area, Central Java. Users can input the geographic coordinates (latitude and longitude) of their current position using the “Get Lokasi” button. In addition, users can select the tower destination from system database.

Figure. 8 Tower database page

The database of BTS towers in Semarang Regency, Central Java is shown on the menu data page in Fig. 8. This page displays the ID, tower site name, longitude, and latitude. In addition, search function has been incorporated to facilitate user queries within the database.

Figure. 9 Results route path finding page

The system will execute the route path finding program to the tower based on the user location. The program will utilize the Dijkstra and A* algorithms to determine the optimal route. The results of this calculation will be presented in the form of runtime and shortest distance, as illustrated in Figure 9. A comparison of the performance of the two algorithms is presented on the Results page, with the duration of processing indicated in the time column. The optimal algorithm is indicated in the results section, specifically in the "algo" column. The shortest route search results are displayed in the form of a digital map, which

can be viewed by pressing the Path and View buttons. These buttons are displayed in Figure 10 using purple lines.

Figure. 10 The shortest route page

B. Path-finding Testing

Shortest route testing stages using A* and Dijkstra. The following is an example of manual route testing, where the user is at Telkomsel Pahlawan Semarang Office at Jalan Pahlawan Semarang, wants to go to the tower location at Jalan Veteran Semarang. The test graph path is shown in Figure 11, with point A as the current position and point W as the destination point. Jalan Veteran Semarang is shown in nodes H, O, N, V, and W. Jalan Pahlawan Semarang is shown in nodes A and B. The other nodes are winding roads such as Jalan Gergaji Pelem, Jalan Gergaji Balekambang, and Jalan Menteri Supeno Selatan.

Figure. 11 Graf Jl. Pahlawan to Jl. Veteran

In the manual calculation of Dijkstra's algorithm, it starts from node A with a distance weight of 550, which ends with node V with a final weight of 1460. In the system, Dijkstra obtained a processing time of 0.007 seconds with a distance of 1492.31 meters. The manual A* calculation calculates the original distance weight and the estimated weight shown in red. It starts by calculating the routes A to B and B to C. Which then compares the route C to D with C - R, where the estimated route C to D is smaller than the route C to R. The comparison process is carried out when there are several nodes connected to the current node. The process ends by comparing node V to W with an estimate of 1480 with node V to I with an estimate of 1860. Point W is the destination point so it is chosen to be the closing node of the recommended route. In testing the system obtained a distance of 1492.31 meters with a processing time of 0.32 seconds. The shortest route using Dijkstra and A* produces the same route, namely A-B-C-R-Q-P-O-N-V-W, resulting in the graph in Figure 12.

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Figure. 12 Results shortes route from A to W

The shortest route to the tower is shown in Figure 13 in purple color, namely users heading to Jalan Pahlawan, Jalan Gergaji Pelem, Jalan Gergaji V, Jalan Metri Supeno Selatan, Jalan Gergaji Balekambang IV, Jalan Gergaji Balekambang Raya, and Jalan Veteran Semarang.

Figure. 13 Shortest route on a digital map

The 82 tests employing randomized routes are summarized in Table II for the Dijkstra algorithm and Table III for the A* algorithm. The current position is given differently to test the system's ability to find the closest route.

TABLE II: ROUTE PATH FINDING USING DIJKSTRA

No	Current Position	Destination Position	Dijkstra	
			Distance (m)	Runtime (s)
1	Jl. Pahlawan (-6.993196, 110.421567)	Jl. Veteran (-6.995266, 110.412491)	1492.31	0.007
2	Jl. Suburan (-6.9916, 110.4312)	Jl. Karangsari III (-6.99128, 110.43122)	2407.89	0.047
3	Jl. Pemuda (-6.96079, 110.391685)	Jl. Marina Raya (-6.960408, 110.3927)	5015.40	0.078
4	Jl. Puri Anjasmoro (-6.9678, 110.3894)	Jl. Puri Maerokoco (-6.9624, 110.3862)	1350.02	0
5	Jl. Menteri Supeno	Jl. Bandara Ahmad Yani	6344.16	0.330

No	Current Position	Destination Position	Dijkstra	
			Distance (m)	Runtime (s)
...
78	Jl. Puri Maerokoco (-6.962515, 110.385547)	Jl. Tawang Sari I (-6.97159, 110.38777)	1582.30	0
79	Jl. Puri Eksekutif (-6.965492, 110.376657)	Jl. Siliwangi (-6.98507, 110.38320)	3060.34	0.015
80	Jl. Marina Raya (-6.95514, 110.39288)	Jl. Semarang Indah (-6.95691, 110.39606)	2135.58	0.019
81	Jl. Arteri Utara (-6.978869, 110.4054444)	Jl. Indraprasta (-6.97842, 110.40689)	3777.06	0.126
82	Jl. Puri Anjasmoro (-6.967339, 110.374032)	Jl. Bendera Ahmad Yani (-6.97979, 110.37799)	3654.89	0.029

In Table II, Dijkstra successfully found the shortest route with low processing time. The majority are less than one second and even reach 0 seconds. Processing times of 0 (zero) are often found at distances of less than 1,000 meters. Dijkstra's average value for getting a route is 0.064 seconds with a standard deviation of 0.122.

TABLE III: ROUTE PATH FINDING USING A*

No	Current Position	Destination Position	A*	
			Distance (m)	Runtime (d)
1	Jl. Pahlawan (-6.993196, 110.421567)	Jl. Veteran (-6.995266, 110.412491)	1492.31	0.328
2	Jl. Suburan (-6.9916, 110.4312)	Jl. Karangsari III (-6.99128, 110.43122)	2407.89	0.588
3	Jl. Pemuda (-6.96079, 110.391685)	Jl. Marina Raya (-6.960408, 110.3927)	5015.40	0.656
4	Jl. Puri Anjasmoro (-6.9678, 110.3894)	Jl. Puri Maerokoco (-6.9624, 110.3862)	1350.02	0.580

No	Current Position	Destination Position	A*	
			Distance (m)	Runtime (d)
5	Jl. Menteri Supeno (-6.9932, 110.4215)	Jl. Bandara Ahmad Yani (-6.9023, 110.37693)	6344.16	0.722
...
78	Jl. Puri Maerokoco (-6.962515, 110.385547)	Jl. Tawangsari I (-6.97159, 110.38777)	1582.30	0.602
79	Jl. Puri Eksekutif (-6.965492, 110.376657)	Jl. Siliwangi (-6.98507, 110.38320)	3060.34	0.611
80	Jl. Marina Raya (-6.95514, 110.39288)	Jl. Semarang Indah (-6.95691, 110.39606)	2135.58	0.633
81	Jl. Arteri Utara (-6.978869, 110.405444)	Jl. Indraprasta (-6.97842, 110.40689)	3777.06	0.663
82	Jl. Puri Anjasmoro (-6.967339, 110.374032)	Jl. Bandara Ahmad Yani (-6.97979, 110.37799)	3654.89	0.615

The results in A* and Dijkstra show the same distance and shortest route. The A* algorithm takes less than a second to get the closest route. With an average processing time of 0.654 seconds and a standard deviation of 0.182. In this case, the A* algorithm is slower than Dijkstra. This decrease in performance is due to the ineffectiveness of the heuristic function on small-scale graphs. The heuristic calculation of Euclidean distance does not provide a significant advantage over Dijkstra's deterministic approach.

C. Evaluation System

The objective of the testing process is to obtain an overview of the system functionality in accordance with the software requirements. The testing process utilizes a black-box to identify any system disfunctions, such as logic errors or absent application features.

TABLE IV: SYSTEM ACCESS TESTING

No	Study Case	Input	Expected Output	Results
1	In-browser system access	Url	Show login page	Success
2	Admin Login	Username admin, Password admin	Show an Admin Dashboard page showing all results and user login settings.	Success
3	User Login	Username user, Password user.	Shows the user dashboard page	Success
4	User Registration	Fullname, Username, Password, Password Confirmation	Shows the user registration page	Success

System access testing is a methodical evaluation that determines the system's accessibility and functionality. The test results are outlined in Table IV. In this test, the system is first accessed by entering the system URL to determine whether it is accessible through a browser. Additionally, testing access between standard users and administrative users involves entering username and password information. During the data input testing process, several variations are carried out, including leaving the username and password blank, inputting a password without a username, and inputting a username without a password. The test scenario involving the username and password input results in a login failure. The testing phase concludes with the registration process for users.

TABLE V: ROUTE PATH FINDING TESTING

No	Study Case	Input	Expected Output	Results
1	Calculate shortest route	Current position of the user, and tower destination location	Shows the results page of the Dijkstra and A* algorithms process	Success
2	The data menu page displays the tower database	Menu data	Shows a table data of BTS towers in the Semarang Regency area	Success
3	The result page	Menu results	Display the results of A*	Success

No	Study Case	Input	Expected Output	Results
	displays the shortest route results		and Dijkstra calculations in table form	
4	Display the shortest route map	In the menu results and click view button	Display the shortest route on a digital map	Success

Table V is the result of testing the shortest route search, the purpose of which were to ascertain the flow of the search process. In this case, we're testing how the system responds when the user searches for the shortest route. The user will see tower data and route details recommended by A* and Dijkstra. Black-box method testing shows that the system has been implemented properly, and the results of system functionality tests always run as expected.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the design and development of a web-based geographic information system to find the shortest route to the tower in the Semarang Regency, Indonesia using the A* and Dijkstra algorithms, it can be concluded that this research produces a geographic information system that can be accessed via the web. The ability of the system to find the closest route can be a supporting tool for technicians to get to the tower faster for the maintenance and maintenance process.

Finding the shortest route using the A* algorithm takes 0.654 ± 0.182 seconds to determine the shortest route, 10 times slower than Dijkstra with a time of 0.064 ± 0.122 seconds. On small graphs, Dijkstra is more optimal due to minimal computational overhead. However, Dijkstra's optimization result is not always optimal depending on the large graph. For further research, an algorithm is developed that considers the factors of red lights, emergency events, and the level of congestion on the road. In addition, testing on more complex region spaces with large graphs.

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